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Review Article

Herbal Cosmetic: An Best Approach For Treating Skin Disorders

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ABSTRACT

India is a focus for development of Ayurveda, Unani, Siddha, Homoeopathy, and other natural herbs-based health knowledge (AYUSH). Ayush Pharmaceutical industriousness having great possible and contingency for saundarya prasadka group (herbal costumer) development in future. Saundarya prasadak are the formulations, which represent cosmetic base which related with known Ayurveda, Siddha and Unani (ASU) medicines active component. In traditional period people were used lepa, Alepa, Pralepa, Udavartan, etc. for beauty purpose. A herb is a plant or plant extract which obtained naturally from nature including leaves, bark, seeds, stems and flowers which are full of nourishing, nutritional and healing elements. Cosmetics alone cannot take care of skin and others body parts; it requires association of active constituents. Herbal cosmetics have important fashion ability among the population. Herbal cosmetics products claimed to have efficacy and natural adequacy due to routine use in day-to-day life and avoid the adverse effects which are generally seen in synthetic products. The current article deals with the literature of herbal cosmetic and plants related to present status, treatment of ailments and properties related to herbal cosmetic and plants.

INTRODUCTION

The word cosmetic came from the Greek word “Kosm tikos” meaning having the power, arrangement, and skill in decorating¹. Herbal cosmetics are also called “natural cosmetics”. The

demand for herbal drugs is increase due to lack of their side effects². At the beginning of civilization; there were no fancy fairness creams or any other cosmetics surgeries. Raymond Reed, launching member of the US society of cosmetics druggist in

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1961 originally used the term cosmeceuticals. He used the word cosmeceuticals to explain active and science-based cosmetics. The term cosmeceuticals were further used by Dr Albert Kligman in the time 1984 to relate the substances that have both cosmetic and therapeutic benefits³. Cosmeceuticals are cosmetic and pharmaceutical intended to enhance beauty and health through constituents that impact the skin's natural texture and body function⁴. In the beginning, only the information about nature was aggregated in the Ayurveda⁵. The only factor they had to calculate was the knowledge of nature collected in the Ayurveda. Ayurveda knowledge had employed numerous herbs to form cosmetics for beautification and protection from external effects. The natural content within botanicals does not cause any side effects on body; rather enriches the body with nutrients and other useful minerals. As per Drug and Cosmetics Act cosmetics are defined as particles intended to be rubbed, poured or spread on, introduced into or applied to the body or any part of body for cleaning, beautifying, promoting attractiveness, or altering the appearance. The cosmetic does not come under the practice of drug license. There is a common belief that chemical based cosmetics are dangerous to the skin and this increased awareness among consumers for herbal products. Therefore, demand for natural products and natural extract in cosmetics formulations increases. The increased demand for natural products has created new avenues in cosmeceutical market. Drug and Cosmetics Act specifies that herbs and essential oil employed in cosmetics must not claim to access beyond the skin layers of the body nor should have any therapeutical side-effects⁶. Herbal cosmetics, refere as products, are formulated, using permissible cosmetic constituents to make base in which one or further herbal constituents are used to give defined cosmetic benefits, shall be called as "Herbal Cosmetics". The history of the herbal

cosmetics industry from about six centuries back includes veritably dark chapters in European and Western countries. The early mixture that was used in Europe for purpose, were so potent that frequently led to paralyse, strokes, or death⁷. There are wide variety of herbal cosmetics that are produced and are generally used for daily purposes. Natural cosmetics are composed entirely of herbs and bushes, which is their best quality. The natural content in the herbs doesn't have any side effect on the body; rather enhances the body with, supplements and other helpful minerals. The plants used in herbal cosmetics, such as saffron (Kesar), ashwagandha, and sandalwood (Chandan), are extended to contain healthy nutrients and all the vibrant necessary ingredients. It is estimated that flavour's areas are employed far and wide, although only about 70 spices are officially honoured. The global herbal industry is currently estimated to be worth more than US \$10 billion and growing at a pace of 3% per year due to rising demand for ethnic foods, natural species, and innovations in beverage goods as well as increased reused food consumption. Regarding manufacturing and consumption, the biggest requests are in Europe, followed by Asia⁸. Herbal medicine includes herbs, herbal medications, and finished herbal products. In some countries, herbal drugs may contain, by tradition, natural organic or inorganic active constituents that are not of herbal plant origin (e.g., animal and mineral materials). Raw plant components such as leaves, flowers, fruit, seeds, stalks, wood, roots, rhizomes, or other plant parts, whether whole, broken, or powdered, are included in the category of herbs. Along with herbs, herbal materials also include fresh juices, gums, essential oils, resins, and dry powdered herb material. The material may be processed using unique methods in some nations, such as steaming, roasting, or stir-baking it with honey, alcoholic beverages, or other ingredients. Finished herbal products refer to

herbal medications made from one or more herbs, but the term "admixture herbal product" can also be used, if further more than one ingredient is used. They also include medicines made by steaming or heating herbal ingredients in alcohol, honey, or through other processes. Still, finished products or herbal products that have been masked with excipients are not included.

Present status

Today herbalists, believe to help people make their good health with the help of natural sources. herbs are considered to be food rather than medicine because they are complete, all- natural, and pure, as nature intended. When herbs are taken in the body, the body starts to get clean, it starts purifying itself. Unlike chemically synthesized, largely concentrated medicines that may produce numerous side effects, can effectively realifing the body. Herbs do not give instant cures, but rather offer a way to put the body in a proper tune with nature9-10.

Advantages of Herbal Cosmetics over Synthetic

Herbal cosmetics are the ultramodern trend in the field of beauty and fashion. These agents are gaining popularity. As currently, most women prefer natural products over chemicals for their particular care to enhance their beauty as these products supply the body with nutrients and enhance health and provide satisfaction because they lack synthetic chemicals and have considerably fewer side effects than synthetic cosmetics. The following are some benefits of utilising natural cosmetics that make them preferable to synthetic ones.

1. Natural products¹¹.
2. Safe to use¹².
3. Compatible with all skin types¹³.
4. Wide selection to choose from¹⁴.
5. No side effects.
6. Not tested on animals.

Marketed products of Herbal Cosmetics⁸

Various retailed skincare products of herbal cosmetic are given in the table below.

Table 1: Herbal skincare product.

Sr. No	Products	Product Name
1	Face pack	Amazine Herbal Scars Face Pack
2	Massage gel	Amazine herbal fruit massage gel
3	Gel	Dr . Jain’s Forest cucumber
4	Face wash	Combi neem Facewash
5	Cream	Vicco turmeric cream
6	Face scrub	Aloe indica face scrub
7	Cold cream	Gayatri papaya & strawberry cold cream
8	Face powder	Agarwal tulsi face powder

Table 2: Herbal hair care products

Sr. No.	Products	Product Name
1	Shampoo	Agarwal honey aloe vera shampoo
2	Anti-dandruff shampoo	Himalaya antidandruff shampoo
3	Hair gel	Aroma sikakai & tulsi hair gel
4	Hair conditioner	Vedico aloeare hair conditioner
5	Hair color	Crown Heena hair colors
6	Hair oil	Prakriti sesam gold hair oil

Table 3: Herbal Lip Care

Sr. No.	Products	Product Name
1	Lip gloss	Komet kozmetik lip gloss
2	Lip plumper	Ruhi lip plumper
3	Lipstick	Kamey lipstick
4	Lip balm	Pallido lip balm

Table 4: Herbal Eyecare Products

Sr. No.	Products	Product Name
1	Eye shadow	Matrix eye shadow
2	Eyeliners	Tonnie eyeliners
3	Mascaras	Uniclor mascararas
4	Eye pencils	Organic rose eye pencils
5	Perfumes	Devy perfumes
6	Deodorants	Always deodorants
7	Soaps	Carmino herbal soaps
8	Foundations	Carmine foundations

Herbal for various skin problem

Table 5: Skin problem and herbs2

Sr. No.	Skin problem	Herbs
1	Dry skin	Coconut oil, Sunflower oil, Aloe Vera
2	Anti-aging	Carrot, Ginkgo, Rhodiola Rosea
3	Dandruff	Henna, Neem, Shikakai
4	Skin protection	Green Tea, Calendula, Turmeric
5	Haircare	Amla, Coconut oil, Almond oil, Arachis Oil, Castor oil, Eucalyptus Oil, Rose oil, Citronella oil, Olive oil, Sunflower oil
6	Antioxidant Activities	Tamarind, Pomegranate, Liquorice

LIST OF HERBS

1. Amla

Scientific name: Emblica Officinalis Linn.

Family: Euphorbiaceae.

Fig 1. Fruit of Amla

Chemical Constituents:

Vitamin C, phyllembin, gallic acid 5% and phyllemblic acid 6.3%, 5% tannin, lipids 6 %, and emblicol, oil are linoleic (44.0%), palmitic (2.99%) oleic (28.40%), linolenic (8.78%), myristic acid (0.95). stearic (2.15%), and Proteolytic and lipolytic enzymes¹⁵.

Traditional uses:

Fruit extract possesses antioxidant properties, Treat skin pigmentation, good skin tone, prevents dandruff, Tonic to the brain, Used in diarrhoea and convalescent stages of typhoid and other fevers¹⁶.

Pharmacological activity:

Ulcer protective and healing¹⁷, Inhibition of lipid peroxidation¹⁸, Antioxidant, cytoprotective and

immunomodulating¹⁹, Anti-tumour²⁰, Cough suppression²¹, Anti snake venom²², Hypolipidemic and ant atherosclerotic²³, Anti-radiatio²⁴, Maintaining homeostasis and increasing resistance²⁵, Lowering of serum enzymes²⁶, Inhibition of hepatotoxicity²⁷, Inhibition of hyperthermia and writhing²⁸, Antibacterial²⁹, Anti-inflammatory³⁰, Antimicrobial³¹, Radical scavenging³², Anti-hepatocarcinogenic³³, Memory elevating³⁴.

2. Coriander

Scientific name: Coriandrum sativum L.

Family: Umbelliferae

Fig 2. Seeds of coriander

Alkaloids, including oxycanthine, epiberberine, palmatine, dehydrocaroline, jatrorhizine, columbamine, karachine, dihydrokarachine, taximaline, and oxyberberine, are among the chemical components.³⁵⁻³⁶

Traditional uses:

Treat rashes and skin burn, antibacterial, detoxifier, act as a stimulant, aromatic and carminative used as a gargle in sore throat and stomatitis, headache, purgatives, used as a flavour in various commercial foods. Act as a hemostat and thus stop bleeding in epistaxis³⁷.

Pharmacological Action:

The anxiolytic³⁸, Antidepressant³⁹, Sedative-hypnotic⁴⁰, Anticonvulsant⁴¹, Effect on memory⁴², Orofacial dyskinesia⁴³, Neuroprotective⁴⁴, Antibacterial, antifungal, anthelmintic and insecticidal⁴⁵, Antioxidant⁴⁶, Hypolipidemic⁴⁷, Anti-inflammatory and analgesic⁴⁸, Antidiabetic⁴⁹, Mutagenic and antimutagenic⁵⁰, Anticancer⁵¹, Cardiovascular⁵², Gastrointestinal⁵³, Hepatoprotective⁵⁴, Deodorizing⁵⁵,

Detoxification⁵⁶, Diuretic⁵⁷, Dermatological⁵⁸, Effect on fertility⁵⁹, Anti-inflammatory⁶⁰.

3. Daruharidra

Scientific name: Berberis aristata

Family: Baeberidaceae

Fig 3. Stem of Daruharidra

Chemical constituents:

alkaloids which are berberine, Berberine, oxycanthine, epiberberine, palmatine, dehydrocaroline, jatrorrhizine, columbamine, karachine, dihydrokarachine, taximaline, oxyberberine, aromoline. alkaloids, pakistanine, 1-O methyl pakistanine, pseudopalmatine chloride and pseudoberberine chloride⁶¹.

Traditional uses:

Beneficial for skin problems like inflammation and psoriasis, Act as a tonic and also in the preparations of formulations for treating eye diseases, jaundice, diarrhoea, syphilis, chronic rheumatism, and urinary disorders⁶².

Pharmacological Action:

Antidiabetic⁶³, Antidepressant⁶⁴, Anti-inflammatory⁶⁵, Antimicrobial⁶⁶, Immunomodulatory⁶⁷, Influence on T-Cell Mediated Immunity⁶⁸, Hepatoprotective⁶⁹, Ocular Trachoma Infections⁷⁰, Cardiovascular Effects, Antihyperlipidemic activity⁷¹, anti-tumor⁷².

4. Haritaki

Scientific name: Terminalia chebul

Family: Combretaceae

Fig 4. Haritaki fruit

Chemical constituents: tannins contain phenolic carboxylic acids like gallic acid, ellagic acid, chebulic acid, and Gallo tannins, Ellagitannin such as punacalagin, casuarinin, corilagin, and terchebulin, and others such as chebulanin, neochebulinic acid, chebulagic acid and chebulinic acid. The tannin content varies with the geological variation. Flavonol glycosides, triterpenoids, coumarin conjugated with gallic acid called chebulin⁷³⁻⁷⁴.

Traditional uses:

Fever, cough, diarrhoea, gastroenteritis, skin diseases, candidiasis, urinary tract infection and wound infections, and Antibacterial Activity⁷⁵

Pharmacological Action:

Wound healing⁷⁶, Antimicrobial⁷⁷, Antibacterial and antifungal⁷⁸, Antihyperglycemic effect⁷⁹, Antioxidant⁸⁰, Anticlastogenic Effect⁸¹, Immunomodulatory⁸², Radiation protection⁸³, Anti caries agent⁸⁴, Gastrointestinal motility⁸⁵, Cardioprotective⁸⁶, Antiaging⁸⁷, Anti lithiatic⁸⁸, Inhibition of cancer cell growth⁸⁹, Bactericidal activity⁹⁰, Antiviral, Radio protecting Ability and Phytochemical Analysis⁹², Anti-ulcerogenic⁹³.

5. Jatamansi

Scientific name: Nardostachys jatamansi

Family: Valerianaceae

Fig 5. Roots of Jatamansi

Chemical constituents:

Nardostachone, Tetrahydronardostachone, β - Maaliene, Tetrahydronardostachol, Tetrahydronardostachane, Jatamansinone, Nardol, Angelcin, Jatamansic Acid, Seychellene, Seychelane, Valernanone, β -Cedrene, Tricyclovetivene,

Gama-Patchoulene, Seychellanol, Seychellanodiol, Alpha -Patchoulene, Beta -Patchoulene, Patchouli alcohol, Norseychellanone, Dihydrojatamansin, Jatamol, Jatamansonol⁹⁴⁻⁹⁵.

Traditional uses:

Acting as a tonic, stimulant, and antiseptic. It has antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, and antioxidant effects. Other treatments of this drug may include headache, excitement, menopausal symptoms, flatulence, epilepsy, fungal disease, hyperlipidemia, and intestinal colic⁹⁶.

Pharmacological action:

Antioxidant Activity⁹⁷, Anti Neuroinflammatory Effects⁹⁸, Premenstrual Syndrome⁹⁹, Anticonvulsant and Neurotoxicity Profile¹⁰⁰, chronic fatigue syndrome¹⁰¹, Anxiety and Insomnia¹⁰², Cardiac Function¹⁰³, Anti-Fungal¹⁰⁴, Anticancer¹⁰⁵, Hepatoprotective¹⁰⁶, Antidiabetic action¹⁰⁷, Neuroprotective¹⁰⁸, Nootropic movement¹⁰⁹.

6. Khus-Khus Grass

Scientific name: Chrysopogon zizanioides

Family: Poaceae

Fig 6. Khus grass roots

Chemical constituents:

70–90% of oil components with varying ratios of hydrocarbons, aldehydes, alcohols, esters, ketones, acids, Khusimol, vetivones, isovelencenol, and zizanioic acid, Khusinol, Epiglobulol, Spathulenol, Khusol, Khusimone, nootkatone acid, and Khusinol acetate, Methyl isovalencenate, Selina-4,7-diene, β -Selinene, γ -Selinene, δ -Selinene, Cascarilladiene, β -cyperone, β -agarofuran, β -Eudesmol, camphor, α -eudesmol, γ -eudesmol¹¹⁰⁻¹¹¹.

Traditional uses:

Reduce the effect of heat, it is specially use for oily skin and acne, relieves genital disorders such as urinary calculi, dysuria, and spermatorrhoea reduces fatigue, acts as cardioprotective, and cures anorexia, diarrhoea, asthma, tuberculosis, and cough¹¹²

Pharmacological action:

Anticancer¹¹³, antimicrobial¹¹⁴, Anticonvulsant¹¹⁵, Antioxidant¹¹⁶, Anti-inflammatory¹¹⁷, Anti-melanogenesis¹¹⁸, Mosquito repellent¹¹⁹, Effect on anxiety¹²⁰, Acaricidal¹²¹, Hypoglycaemic¹²², Antidepressant effect¹²³, Protective effect against Cisplatin- induced toxicity¹²⁴, Antidiuretic activity¹²⁵, Sedative activity¹²⁶, Antifungal activity¹²⁷.

7. Kushta

Scientific name: Saussurea lappa C B Clarke.

Family: Compositae

Fig 7. Kushta Roots

Chemical constituent:

Resins, alkaloids, a solid resin, salt of valeric acid, astringent and ash that contains manganese, Camphene 0.04%, phellandrene 0.4%, terpene alcohol 0.2%, A- costene 6.0%, B-costene 6.0%, aplotaxene 20.0%, costol 7.0%, di-hydrocostus lactone 15.0%, costus lactone 10.0%, costic acid 14%, Glycoside¹²⁸.

Traditional uses:

Diuretic, Anthelmintic, Skin diseases, Jaundice, Asthama, Malaria, Leprosy, Aromatic stimulant, Antiseptic¹²⁹.

Pharmacological Action:

Anti-spasmodic activity¹³⁰, Anti-inflammatory¹³¹, anti- cancer/Antitumor¹³², Hepatoprotective¹³³, Anti-ulcer and sialagogic¹³⁴, Immunomodulator¹³⁵, Hypolipidemic¹³⁶, Antiparasitic¹³⁷, Antifeedant¹³⁸, CNS-Depressant¹³⁹.

8. Liquorice

Scientific name: Glycyrrhiza glabra L.

Family: Fabaceae

Fig 8. Licorice Root

Chemical constituents:

Glycyrrhizin, Liquiritin, Isoliquiritin, Liquiritigenin, Isoliquiritigenin, Neoisoliquiritin, Licoflavonol, Isolicoflavonol, Licochalcone A, LicochalconeB, Licochalcone C, Licochalcone D, Licoricone, Glabridin, Glabrene, Glabranin, Uralenin, Licocoumarin A, Kanzonol R140.

Traditional uses:

Protecting skin from premature ageing, protect skin from sunburn, fever, hypertension, gastric ulcers, paralysis, rheumatism, sexual weakness, hemorrhagic diseases, respiratory diseases, viral cough, viral hepatitis, inflammation, and other diseases141.

Pharmacological action:

Anti-inflammatory Effects142, Antiviral Effects143, ACE2 Inhibition144, Antibacterial, and Antifungal Effects145, Immunomodulatory Effects146, Anti- Pulmonary Fibrosis Effects147, Protection of Other Organs148.

9. Lodhra

Scientific name: Symplocos racemosa

Family: Symplococaceae

Fig 9. Lodhra Bark

Chemical constituents:

Flavanol glycoside, Alkaloids loturine, Isoloturine, Oleonealic acid, Betulinic acid, Ellagic acid, Beta-Sitosterol, Loturine, Salireposide, Saponin, Tannins, Phenol149.

Traditional uses:

Prevent wrinkles, control acne, mainly used for snakebite and scorpion sting, treatment of diarrhea, dysentery, spongy gum, bleeding, leprosy, dropsy, abortion, miscarriages, ulcers of the vagina, uterine disorders, arrests, uterine hemorrhages, abnormal secretions, aphrodisiac150.

Pharmacological actions:

The anti-acne effect151, Anti-inflammatory and Analgesic152, Antioxidant153, Antibacterial154.

10. Manjistha

Scientific name: Rubia cordifolia Linn

Family: Rubiaceae

Fig 10. Manjistha Stem

Chemical constituents:

Anthraquinones, Naphthoquinones, Cyclic Hexapeptides, Triterpenoids, organic acids, polysaccharides, rubilactone, rubiasin A-C, β -sitostenone, β - sitosterol, 5-methoxygeniposidic acid, 6-methoxygeniposidic acid155.

Traditional uses:

Acne, infection, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, Hematemesis, epistaxis, flooding, spotting, traumatic bleeding, amenorrhea caused by obstruction, pain caused by injuries from falls156. Pharmacological Actions: Antitumor157, Immunomodulation158, Anti-Inflammation159, Neuroprotection160, Antioxidation161, Toxicology162, Anti-osteoclastogenesis163.

11. Masoor

Scientific name: Lens esculenta

Family: Papilionaceae

Fig 11. Masoor Seeds

Chemical constituent:

Isoleucine, Leucine, Lysine Methionine, Phenylaniline + tyrosine, Threonine, Tryptophan, Valine, Histidine Limiting amino acid, Sulphur amino acids, Crude protein Total lipids, Total carbohydrates, Crude fiber, Ash, Sodium, Potassium Phosphorus, Calcium, Iron Copper, Zinc, Manganese A164.

Traditional uses:

Fever, eye diseases, tan removal, pain, Antioxidant165.

Pharmacological Actions:

Anti-hyperlipidemic, Anti-diarrheal, Anti spasmodic, Bronchodilator, Vasodilator, Antioxidant, Nephro Protective166.

12. Nutgrass

Scientific name: Cyperus rotundus L.

Family: Cyperaceae

Fig 12. Rhizomes of Nutgrass

Chemical constituents:

α -cyperolone, β -cyperone, p -cymol, calcium, camphene, copaene, cyperene, cyperenone, cyperol, cyperolone, caryophyllene, cyperotundone, d-copadiene, d- epoxyguaiene, isocyperol, isokobusone, kobusone, limonene, linoleic-acid, linolenic acid, mustakone, myristic acid, oleanolic acid, oleic acid, β -pinene, patchoulone, rotundene, rotundenol, rotundone, α -rotunol, β -rotunol, β -selinene, selinatriene, sitosterol, stearic acid, sugeonol, and sugetriol, f alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, phenols, tannins, steroids, starch and many novel sesquiterpenoid167-168.

Traditional uses:

Reduce skin aging, pigment, melanin, treatment of stomach and bowel disorders and inflammatory diseases analgesic, antibacterial169.

Pharmacological action: Antioxidant property170, Wound healing171, Anti-inflammatory172, Antidiarrheal173, Antihyperglycemic174, Antiplatelet175, Gastroprotective176, Anti-allergic177, Neuroprotective178, Antiviral179.

13. Nagakesar

Scientific name: Mesua ferrea Linn

Family: Guttiferae

Fig 13. Nagakesar Buds

Chemical constituents:

Mesulol, Mammeisin, Mesuagin, Mammeigin, Mesuabixanthone A and Mesuabixanthone B, Mesuaferrol, Mesuaxanthone A, Mesuaxanthone B, Euxanthone, Mesuaferrone A, Mesuaferrone B, Mesuanic acid180.

Traditional uses:

Antiseptic, purgative, blood purifier, worm control, tonic properties to treat fever, cold, asthma and as carminative, expectorant, cardiotoxic, diuretic and antipyretic, agent antidotes for snakebite and scorpion sting, cutaneous infection, sores, scabies, wounds and rheumatism, stomachic, expectorant and astringent180.

Pharmacological action:

Disinfection studies181, Antioxidant and hepatoprotective182, Analgesic183, Antispasmodic184, Immunomodulatory185, Anti-convulsant186, Anti-ulcer187, Anti-microbial188, Anti-arthritis180.

14. Neem

Scientific name: Azadirachta indica

Family: Meliaceae

Fig 14. Neem Leaves

Chemical constituents:

Nimbin, Nimbin, Nimbidinin, Nimbolide, and Nimbidic acid. Nimbidin and sodium Nimbidate, tannin, tricyclic diterpenoids, margolone, margolonone, cyclic trisulphide, tetrasulphide¹⁸⁹.

Traditional uses:

antifungal, provide Cooling effect, Antiarthritis, antiulcer effects, antihistamine, reduced blood glucose level, antifungal activity against, diuretic agent, and antimalarial activity¹⁹⁰.

Pharmacological action:

The analgesic effect¹⁹¹, Antifungal effects¹⁹², Antibacterial¹⁹³, Antiviral¹⁹⁴, Hepatoprotective¹⁹⁵, Antihyperglycemic agent¹⁹⁶.

15. Orange peel

Scientific name: Citrus aurantium L

Family: Rutaceae

Fig15. Orange peel powder

Chemical constituents:

Isoquinoline alkaloid, Synephrine, 5-methyl tyramine, Alkaloid- Diphenylamine Triterpene - Limonin, Nomilin, Sesquiterpene- α -Bergamotene, β -Bisabolene, β Caryophyllene, Monoterpene- Linalool, Linalool acetate and Alkaloid 3-(but-cis-1-enyl) pyridine, Geranyl-oxy pyranocoumarin, Seselin, Suberosin, Xanthoxyletin, Xanthyletin¹⁹⁷⁻¹⁹⁸.

Traditional uses:

Helps to lighten and brighten the skin, fight acne, moisturise the skin, stomach ache, vomiting, blood pressure, cough, cold, bronchitis, earache, dysentery, diarrhea, abdominal pain and fever, UTI ailments, influenza, insomnia, a cardiovascular analeptic, antispasmodic, cold, sedative, digestive, urinary tract infections¹⁹⁹.

Pharmacological action:

Laxative¹⁹⁹, Antiulcer²⁰⁰, Antifungal²⁰¹, Antiyeast activity²⁰², Antiulcer²⁰³, Immunosuppressant²⁰⁴, Antimicrobial²⁰⁵ Protein Binding Activity¹⁹⁹.

16. Padmakashta

Scientific name: Prunus padus L.

Family: Rosaceae

Fig 16. Padmakashta Bark

Chemical constituents:

beta-carotene, anthocyanins, Tocopherols and Vitamin C, Non- glycosylated pentacyclic triterpenoids, malic acid, citric acid and tartaric acid, shikimic acid, organic acids as oxalic acid, malic acid or fumaric acid, organic acids, polyphenols, monoterpenes and vitamin C, Polyphenols, cinnamic acid, flavonols, benzoic acids, catechins and tannins, quercitrin and quercetin, ellagic acid, gallic acid, and vanillic acid²⁰⁶.

Traditional uses:

Use in the pharmaceutical, food and cosmetics, hypertension, inflammatory diseases, rheumatoid arthritis, asthma and cancer, antioxidant and Nutrients, antibacterial properties²⁰⁷.

Pharmacological actions:

Antioxidant Activity²⁰⁸, Antimicrobial²⁰⁹, Antidiabetic Effect²¹⁰, Cardiovascular²¹¹, Anti-Inflammatory and Anti-Nociceptive Properties²¹².

17. Sariva

Scientific name: Hemidesmus indicus L.

Family: Asclepiadaceae

Fig 17. Sariva Roots

Chemical constituents:

Glycoside, Hemindicusin. Coumarinolignoids, α -amyrin, β amyryl, lupeol acetate, β -sitosterol, hexadecanoic acid, hexatriacontane, lupeol octasonate, crystalline matter, glucose, hemidesmol, hemidesterol, 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy benzaldehyde, resin acid, glucoside, α -amyryl triterpene, β -amyryl triterpene, and benzaldehyde, Isoquercetin, and Rutin²¹³⁻²¹⁴. Traditional uses include treating eczema and psoriasis, syphilis, dyspepsia, leucoderma, persistent fever, asthma, liver ailments, venereal disorders, leprosy, urinary tract infections, and scorching of the body, arthritis, bronchitis, epileptic seizures, high blood pressure, , rheumatism, chronic nervous diseases, impotence, and immune disorders²¹⁵.

Pharmacological action:

Antimicrobial²¹⁶, Anticarcinogenic²¹⁷, Antithrombotic²¹⁸, Wound healing²¹⁵, Antivenom²¹⁹, Anti-ulcer activity²²⁰, Larvicidal²²¹, Anticonvulsant²²², Anti-psychotic and Antidiarrheal²¹⁵.

18. Turmeric

Scientific name: Curcuma longa

Family: Zingiberaceae

Fig 18. Turmeric Rhizome

Chemical constituents:

Flavonoid Curcuminoids, diferuloylmethane, monodexmethoxycurcumin, and bisdesmethoxycurcumin, approximately 90% of the curcuminoid content. Sugars, proteins, and resins, tumerone, atlantone, and zingiberone²²³. Traditional uses: As an anti-inflammatory , hemorrhages and skin diseases like herpes zoster and pemphigus, applied topically for urticaria and skin allergy, for the treatment of jaundice, menstrual difficulties, haematuria, hemorrhage,

sore throat, and wounds, for the treatment of acne, wounds, boils, bruises, blistering, ulcers, eczema, insect bites, parasitic infections²²⁴.

Pharmacological actions:

anti-inflammatory²²⁵, antioxidant²²⁶, hepatoprotective²²⁷, anticarcinogenic²²⁸, antidiabetic²²⁹, antimicrobial²³⁰, antidepressant²³¹, cardiovascular disease²³², gastrointestinal and neurological disorders²³³, Pregnancy/Neonates²²⁴.

19. White Sandalwood

Scientific name: Santalum album L.

Family: Santalaceae

Fig 19. White Sandal heartwood Powder

Chemical constituents: Sesquiterpene, α - santalol and β -santalol, hydrocarbons santene, nor- tricycloekasantalene, and α - and, β -santalenes; the alcohols santenol and teresantalol; the aldehydes nor-tricycloekasantal, and isovaleraldehyde, ketones Isantenone, teresantalic acid occurring partly free and partly in ester and S-santalic acids²³⁴⁻²³⁵.

Traditional uses:

Perfumery, cosmetics, aromatherapy and pharmaceutical industry, flavouring substance in food products, for ornamental and carving work, treating gastric irritability, jaundice, dysentery, tension, and confusion, and also used a blood purifier, anti- poison, tonic for the heart, stomach, and liver, anti-fever, and tonic for poisons., fever, memory improvement and as a blood purifier.

Pharmacological actions: Aromatherapy²³⁶, Antitumor²³⁷, Infantile hyperhidrosis²³⁸, Facial scrub²³⁹, Anti-Helicobacter pylori Compounds from Santalum album²⁴⁰, In Bladder infections²⁴¹, Acute dermatitis, Bronchitis,

Cystitis, Eye diseases, Gonorrhoea, Herpes Zoster Infection, Palpitation, Sunstroke, Urethritis²⁴².

CONCLUSION

Over 70% of the population uses herbal cosmetics. A modern herbal cosmetic has become a significant necessity in daily life. A basis of herbal ingredients is used to create herbal cosmetics, which may contain one or more herbal ingredients to treat a variety of skin issues and to enhance beauty. All of these cosmetic compositions' chemical ingredients include diverse natural components like waxes, liquid natural colours, natural scents, and plant parts like leaves, bark, and flowers, among others. The term "cosmeceuticals" refers to products that sit in the middle of the spectrum between pure cosmetics (like eye shadow and cream) and pure pharmaceuticals (like antibiotics and corticosteroids). Corrective formulation is dependent on natural beauty formulations, which may include additives with aesthetic benefits to replace synthetic components. To demonstrate the effectiveness of herbal cosmetics, more research and development are required in this area. Herbal cosmetics must pass a quality control test. Longer-term safety is anticipated. It appears that the people and tradition have a strong understanding of the therapeutic herbs they use. Numerous plants that people use as cosmetics and to treat dermatological conditions were related in the current study. Some of the plants were created with the dual purposes of beauty and restoration in mind.

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